

Table 2. Effect of P fertilization and moisture regimes^a on P concentration and dry matter yield in some acid soils of Assam, India, 1978.^b

Location of soil	P concentration (%)						Dry matter yield (g/pot)					
	Continuous submergence			Continuous moist			Continuous submergence			Continuous moist		
	0 P	26.4 kg P/ha	52.8 kg P/ha	0 P	26.4 kg P/ha	52.8 kg P/ha	0 P	26.4 kg P/ha	52.8 kg P/ha	0 P	26.4 kg P/ha	52.8 kg P/ha
Titabar	0.136	0.182	0.215	0.093	0.090	0.114	13.13	28.80	34.13	6.97	20.83	17.87
Dergaon	0.171	0.307	0.326	0.093	0.131	0.156	21.80	23.60	36.10	9.87	14.57	13.50
Golaghat	0.185	0.264	0.310	0.110	0.117	0.139	23.20	34.27	30.80	13.10	16.00	16.87
Tengakhat	0.250	0.327	0.361	0.088	0.133	0.151	41.53	48.57	47.77	13.70	20.37	19.27
Mean of all soils	0.186	0.270	0.303	0.096	0.118	0.140	24.92	33.81	37.20	10.91	17.94	16.87
	C.D.(5%) Moisture regimes: 0.0089 Phosphorus levels: 0.0109						C.D.(5%) Moisture regimes: 3.17 Phosphorus levels: 3.88					

^aContinuous submergence: 5-7 cm standing water; continuous moist: moisture tension, 0 bar. ^bAt max tillering stage. Av of 3 replications.

Table 3. Effect of P fertilization and moisture regimes^a on P concentration of grain and yield of rice grain in some acid soils of Assam, India, 1978.^b

Location of soil	P concentration (%) in grain						Grain yield (g/pot)					
	Continuous submergence			Continuous moist			Continuous submergence			Continuous moist		
	0 P	26.4 kg P/ha	52.8 kg P/ha	0 P	26.4 kg P/ha	52.8 kg P/ha	0 P	26.4 kg P/ha	52.8 kg P/ha	0 P	26.4 kg P/ha	52.8 kg P/ha
Titabar	0.276	0.278	0.324	0.235	0.213	0.211	13.30	21.83	22.90	4.43	6.47	9.57
Dergaon	0.248	0.312	0.366	0.190	0.168	0.264	15.37	18.47	18.50	6.77	9.70	11.13
Golaghat	0.215	0.312	0.367	0.191	0.142	0.215	16.63	21.97	24.30	7.33	11.10	10.17
Tengakhat	0.292	0.349	0.373	0.157	0.188	0.247	22.60	24.33	27.77	7.63	11.30	10.63
Mean of all soils	0.258	0.315	0.358	0.193	0.178	0.234	16.97	21.65	23.37	6.54	9.64	10.37
	C.D.(5%) Moisture regimes: 0.021 Phosphorus levels: 0.026						C.D.(5%) Moisture regimes: 1.30 Phosphorus levels: 1.60					

^aContinuous submergence: 5-7 cm standing water; continuous moist: moisture tension, 0 bar. ^bAt grain ripening. Av of 3 replications.

were continuous moist and continuous submergence.

Phosphorus application significantly increased P concentration in dry matter at maximum tillering stage at both moisture regimes (Table 2), but P concentration was higher in continuous submergence. Dry matter yield increases corresponded with increased P concentration under continuous submergence in all four soils. Results were similar in

continuous moist condition, but P concentration and dry matter yield were lower at each level of P application.

P applied to submerged soils caused significant increases in P concentration of grain at ripening stage and increased yield (Table 3). However, in continuous moist condition, there was no such consistency. In 3 of 4 soils, 26.4 kg P/ha decreased P concentration and increased yield, which suggests that yield increase

was achieved by dilution of the plant P concentration. At 52.8 kg P/ha, there was a significant increase in the P concentration in all the soils except that from Titabar. Grain yield increased in Titabar and Dergaon and decreased slightly in Golaghat and Tengakhat.

Results suggest that phosphorus application and continuous submergence improve rice crop performance. *h*

Use of azolla and commercial nitrogen fertilizer in Jorhat, India

H. P. Barthakur and H. Talukdar, Assam Agricultural University, Jorhat 785013, India

Complementary use of azolla and commercial nitrogen fertilizer for rice culture is receiving interest because of the global energy crisis. A 2-year experiment at Jorhat showed that incorporating 5 t fresh azolla/ha just before planting increased yields of Pusa 33 (1979) and Pusa 2-21 (1980) 44% over the control (no nitrogen, no azolla) (see table).

Mean grain yield of rice as affected by incorporation of azolla with and without nitrogen fertilizer, Jorhat, India.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Azolla incorporation		Yield (t/ha)	
	t/ha	Time	Pusa 33 (1979)	Pusa 2-21 (1980)
0	0	—	1.8	1.7
0	1 ^a	After planting	2.5	2.3
0	5	Before planting	2.6	2.5
0	10	Before planting	3.0	2.9
30	5	Before planting	3.4	3.3
30	10	Before planting	3.7	3.5
30	0	—	2.8	2.4
60	0	—	2.9	3.0
LSD (5%) in t/ha			0.6	0.4

^aFresh azolla was inoculated after planting, allowed to grow and then incorporated after 20 days.

Application of 30 kg N (urea)/ha increased yield by 55% in 1979 and 42% in 1980. Application of 30 kg N/ha and 5 t azolla/ha increased yields 86.4% over the control in 1979 and 92% in 1980.

Results showed that inoculating fields

with 1 t fresh azolla/ha after planting and incorporating after 20 days increased yield by 38% in 1979 and 36.5% in 1980. Increased yield caused by raising azolla application from 5 t/ha to 10 t/ha was significant only in 1980.

Rice yields were significantly higher from 30 kg N/ha and 10 t fresh azolla/ha than from single applications of nitrogen in both years. *k*

Effects of growth regulators applied to the main crop on ratoonability of IR9784-52-2-3-2 in pots

Md. Abdul Quddus, scientific officer, Division of Rice Cropping Systems, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute; and J. W. Pendleton, head, Multiple Cropping Department, IRRI

A rice ratoon crop begins growth using carbohydrates left in the stubble and roots after the main crop is harvested. If leaf senescence is early in the main crop, less carbohydrate is accumulated and fewer ratoon tillers grow.

Growth regulators have been reported to delay leaf senescence in certain crops. Growth regulators at various concentrations applied to the main crop at various growth stages were tested for their effect on the ratoon crop in a pot experiment at IRRI during the 1981 dry season.

Aqueous solutions (1, 10, and 100 ppm) of indoleacetic acid (IAA), naphthaleneacetic acid (NAA), gibberellic acid (GA3), and dichlorophenoxy acetic acid (2,4-D) were sprayed (3 ml/plant), and carbofuran at 1 kg ai/ha was broadcast in prill form.

The growth regulators did not significantly affect the yield of the main crop or the ratoon crop (see table). *k*

Effect of growth regulators applied to the main crop on yield and yield components of the ratoon crop of IR9784-52-2-3-2, IRRI, 1981 dry season.^a

Growth regulators	Concn (PPm)	Time of application ^b	Grain yield (g/plant)	Panicles (no./plant)	Filled gras (no./panicle)	100-gain weight (g)
IAA	1	F	15.0	26	28	1.94
		LMS	13.4	25	29	1.91
	10	F	16.7	27	31	1.94
		LMS	14.1	26	29	1.94
	100	F	17.4	27	35	1.94
		LMS	15.3	25	29	1.95
NAA	1	F	13.0	22	38	1.94
		LMS	12.7	22	30	1.95
	10	F	14.6	26	32	1.93
		LMS	15.3	28	28	1.91
	100	F	15.7	26	33	1.91
		LMS	15.9	26	30	1.94
GA3	1	F	15.5	26	31	1.91
		LMS	13.8	24	30	1.96
	10	F	15.0	26	27	1.95
		LMS	18.5	28	30	1.95
	100	F	13.8	24	32	1.96
		LMS	14.9	29	26	1.93
2,4-D	1	F	13.8	24	34	1.93
		LMS	12.3	26	29	1.93
	10	F	16.4	26	33	1.94
		LMS	15.6	26	32	1.92
	100	F	15.9	27	32	1.93
		LMS	16.3	23	31	1.94
Carbofuran	1 kg ai/ha	F	12.3	24	28	1.94
		LMS	15.2	24	29	1.97
Control			17.2	29	32	1.91

^aAnalysis of variance indicated nonsignificant treatment differences at 5% probability level. ^bF = flowering, LMS = late milk stage.

Studies on multiplication of azolla

B. K. Mandal and A. K. Bharati, Agronomy Department, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya Kalyani, Nadia, West Bengal, India

Azolla Azolla pinnata is a floating fern with nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae *Anabaena azollae* in its leaves. Phosphorus (P) fertilizer is necessary for good azolla yields. Azolla is attacked by the larvae of Lepidoptera (Nymphula)

and Diptera (Chironomus) insects that roll the leaves and feed on the plants.

Azolla was multiplied in plots with 5, 10, and 15 cm standing water using 4.4, 8.8, and 13.2 kg P/ha per week and 2 levels of carbofuran (5 and 10 kg/ha). Fifty-four 1-m² plots were inoculated with 300 g freshly collected azolla plants. Breeding plots were harvested weekly and fresh weight was recorded. Total N and P contents were determined (see table).

Results showed that P is essential for azolla multiplication. Plants with P deficiency had reddish brown fronds and roots, and roots were long, fragile, and easily detached. Best growth was obtained by applying 8.8 kg P/ha and 10 kg carbofuran/ha weekly to plots with 10 cm standing water. There was no significant growth difference between plots at 5 cm and 15 cm water depth.

Application of 8.8 kg P/ha and 10 kg carbofuran/ha per week increased N